

**Development of favorite collections &
visualizing user search queries
in CERN Document Server (CDS)**

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Abstract

Invenio is an open source web-based application that implements a digital library or document server, and it's used at CERN as the base of the CERN Document Server Institutional Repository and the Inspire High Energy Physics Subject Repository.

The purpose of this project was to add a new feature to CDS, through which users could manage their own favorite collections on top of existing ones. My work involved adding new features to the WebSearch module, so as to achieve the stated objectives.

Later on, another task was to parse user searched queries so as to provide end-users with a visualized pattern of search, involving global searched terms or terms popular for a particular collection.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Invenio

This digital library is an instance of the Invenio, an open-source digital library framework, that is mainly developed using Python on top of a MySQL database to create a document server, to manage all sorts of files and their corresponding meta-data. The atom in Invenio is the record, which is composed of metadata and can have one or more files associated with it. Through this concept, it's possible to get statistics, extract relations among records, rank them and manage them.

→ Invenio has around 53 modules and is still expanding. [1]

→ Modified 2 modules:

- Webstat (for Task 2 – mentioned later on)
- Websearch (for Task 1 and Task 2)

→ Most of the modifications I did was in the WebSearch Module of Invenio.

→ My work was done in invenio-master branch installation of Invenio v1.1.1.

1.2 CERN Document Server (CDS)

The CERN Document Server holds a document repositories containing over 1 million bibliographic records, more than 400,000 full text documents, of interest to people working in particle physics and related areas. Material covered includes preprints, articles, books, journals, photos, and videos. Services include provision of an institutional repository for CERN documents, to organize and manage them in collections and to archive them.

2. Project Work:

2.1 Task 1: Favorite-Collections

2.1.1 Description :-

To implement a "favorite collections" feature, within Invenio digital library software (<http://invenio-software.org/>) used by CDS, allowing users to manage their favorite collections on top of the existing ones, like Articles, Reports and so on..

2.1.2 Major Technologies involved :-

Python

Python is an easy to learn, powerful programming language. It has efficient high-level data structures and a simple but effective approach to object-oriented programming. Python's elegant syntax and dynamic typing, together with its interpreted nature, make it an ideal language for scripting and rapid application development in many areas on most platforms

MySQL

MySQL open-source relational database management system (RDBMS) is a popular choice of database for use in web applications, and is a central component of the widely used LAMP open source web application software stack.

jQuery Tooltip

jQuery library provides with Tooltips, that can be attached to any DOM element. When you hover the element with your mouse, the title attribute is displayed in a little box next to the element, just like a native tooltip. Tooltips are also useful for form elements, to show some additional information in the context of each field.

2.1.3 Implementation :-

- Through hover-cards, a user could easily add a collection to favorites
- New table in database [stores user & favorite-collection preferences.]
- Writing an interface that loads favorites, once a user logs in.

Add on: websearch_favorite_collection.py

```
def perform_delete_favorite_collection(uID, collID, req):  
    """Delete a collection from favorite(s).  
    @param uID: User ID who wants to add the collection  
    @param collID: collection ID for adding to favorites  
    @param req: returned object from AJAX request  
    """
```

```
def perform_calculate_favorites(uID):  
    """Talks to DB for extracting favorites for a user  
  
    @param uID: User ID of currently logged in user  
    """
```

```
def perform_add_new_favorite(uID, collID, req):  
    """Add collection to favorite(s).  
  
    @param uID: User ID who wants to add the collection  
    @param collID: collection ID for adding to favorites  
    @param req: returned object from AJAX request  
    """
```

Add on: new template for displaying favorites

```
def tpl_favorite_collection(self, fav_data, ln, show_body=True):
    """
    Adds to the body of main search page,
    a column named 'Your Favorite Collection(s)'

    Parameters:
    @param fav_data: Tuples containing the favorites for a user """
```

Steps involved :-

1. All logical statements from invenio.websearch.websearch_favorites .
2. All templates added to invenio.websearch.websearch_templates .
3. In websearch_templates, tpl_narrowsearch() modified to include hover-cards functionality.

Brand New Installation looks something like this:

[Home](#) > arcolife's invenio test installation

Search 878,508 records for:

any field Search Browse

[Search Tips](#) :: [Advanced Search](#)

Narrow by collection:

- [Articles & Preprints](#) (854,773)
 - [Drafts](#) (3) [Articles](#) (280,636) [Notes](#) (21) [Preprints](#) (574,135)
- [Books & Reports](#) (23,732)
 - [Books](#) (5,284) [Theses](#) (18,280) [Reports](#) (5,434)
- [Multimedia & Arts](#) (16)
 - [Poetry](#) (3) [Videos](#) (1) [Pictures](#) (7) [Atlantis Times](#) (5)

Focus on:

- [CERN Divisions](#) (5)
 - [Experimental Physics \(EP\)](#) (1) [Theoretical Physics \(TH\)](#) (4)
- [CERN Experiments](#) (6)
 - [ALEPH](#) (5) [ISOLDE](#) (1)

After adding favorite-collections feature:

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar with the Atlantis Institute logo and the title "ARCOLIFE'S INVENIO TEST INSTALLATION". Below the title are buttons for "Search", "Submit", "Personalize", and "Help". A breadcrumb trail reads "Home > arcolife's invenio test installation".

The main content area displays "Search 878,508 records for:" followed by a search input field, a dropdown menu set to "any field", and "Search" and "Browse" buttons. Below these are links for "Search Tips" and "Advanced Search".

On the left, under "Narrow by collection:", there are four main categories with sub-items and counts:

- Articles & Preprints** (254,773) - Includes "Drafts (3)", "Articles (574,135)", and a highlighted "Add to favorites" button.
- Books & Reports** (23,732) - Includes "Books (5,284)", "Theses (18,280)", and "Reports (5,434)".
- Multimedia & Arts** (16) - Includes "Poetry (3)", "Videos (1)", "Pictures (7)", and "Atlantis Times (5)".

On the right, under "Focus on:", there are three categories:

- CERN Divisions** (5)
- Experimental Physics (EP)** (1) and **Theoretical Physics (TH)** (4)
- CERN Experiments** (6) - Includes "ALEPH (5)" and "ISOLDE (1)".

At the bottom left, "Your favorite collections:" lists "Preprints", "Theses", "Reports", and "Poetry". A "Remove this collection from favorites?" dialog box with a "Yes" button is overlaid on the "Preprints" item.

2.1.4 Future Work :-

The following includes few minor limitations and possible future options:

- “Favorites” feature could be extended to submissions, searches and baskets.
- An addition to be made to drop down list 'personalize' for logged in users.
- Hover-cards instead show up on clicking a small icon instead of '.hover()'

2.2 Task 2: Visualization of popular searched terms

2.2.1 Description :-

To analyze and visualize user search queries, giving options of different views on data, so that a user is easily able to explore interesting patterns among all popular searched terms, arising from different user queries, over the passage of time.

2.2.2 Major Technologies involved :-

Numpy

NumPy is the fundamental package for scientific computing with Python. Its various features are:

- A powerful N-dimensional array object
- Useful linear algebra, Fourier transform, and random number capabilities
- An efficient multi-dimensional container of generic data.
- Arbitrary data-types can be defined.

Visualization Tool – D3

D3.js (or just D3 for Data-Driven Documents) is a JavaScript library that uses digital data to drive the creation and control of dynamic and interactive graphical forms which run in web browsers. It is a tool for data visualization in W3C-compliant computing, making use of the widely implemented Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG), JavaScript, HTML5, and Cascading Style Sheets (CSS3) standards. [2]

Pandas

It is an open source, BSD-licensed data analysis library providing high-performance, easy-to-use data structures and data analysis tools for the Python programming language.

The highlights include → Fast and efficient DataFrame object; Tools for reading and writing data between in-memory data structures and different formats; fancy indexing, and subsetting of large data sets; Time series-functionality.

2.2.3 Implementation :-

- Use of python libraries – pandas and numpy to do intense processing
- Use of json / csv file types for storing the data for visualization (where data is distributed weekly)
- cron job, to update DB with newer queries every week.
- Json should have partial data (dynamic threshold)
Like: first 2000 most used queries.
- Different views for visualization (for global popular terms / Parameter-based).
Like: Popular searched terms, authors, collections,..
- New URL for presenting visualizations on CDS.

Data Structures Used

```
# Structure of pd_dict <= { q_id : 'query_urlargs' }
In [67]: type(pd_dict)
Out[67]: pandas.core.series.Series

# Structure of data <= Data columns: q_id ; u_id ; timestamp
In [68]: type(data)
Out[68]: pandas.core.frame.DataFrame
```

Here:

- *q_id* is the query's id in database
- *u_id* is the user id (if a guest user or a registered user id)
- *Timestamp* is the time at which the search was made
- *query_urlargs* are the arguments passed in the url.

Different types of queries

```
In [335]: parse_qs(pd_dict[10])
```

```
Out[335]:
```

```
{'c': ['SL Notes',  
      'LHC Project Notes',  
      'ATLAS Notes',  
      'CMS Notes',  
      'CERN Archives',  
      'HEP Institutes',  
      'Press Cuttings',  
      'Exhibition Objects',  
      'References in E-prints'],  
 'p': ['author:"Anashin V V*"]}]
```

```
In [75]: parse_qs(pd_dict[3214343])
```

```
Out[75]:
```

```
{'action_search': ['Search'],  
 'f': ['author'],  
 'of': ['hb'],  
 'p': ['Landau, Lev Davidovich'],  
 'rg': ['10'],  
 'sc': ['0'],  
 'so': ['d']}
```

```
from invenio.search_engine import create_basic_search_units  
p = 'author:Ellis OR higgs AND abstract:boson - title:"higgs boson"  
f = 'keyword'  
create_basic_search_units(None, p=p, f=f)
```

```
Out[7]:
```

```
[['+', 'Ellis', 'author', 'w'],  
 ['|', 'higgs', 'keyword', 'w'],  
 ['+', 'boson', 'abstract', 'w'],  
 ['- ', 'higgs boson', 'title', 'a']]
```

Patterns Found :-

<p><u>The actual dataset</u> <u>June-August 2012</u></p> <p>.....</p> <p> -- [1.9M] w_22.csv -- [4.2M] w_23.csv -- [3.7M] w_24.csv -- [3.5M] w_25.csv -- [3.5M] w_26.csv -- [6.9M] w_27.csv -- [3.7M] w_28.csv -- [2.6M] w_29.csv -- [2.6M] w_30.csv</p> <p>.....</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>July 4th - 2012</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Announcement about the Higgs Boson particle</u> [3]</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px; margin: 10px 0;"> <p>[Snapshot of a tweet, supporting the announcement of that discovery]</p> </div>
---	---

- w_22.csv - smallest file; 22nd WeekOfYear ..was actually 1st week of June 2012.
It had only 3 days (upto Sunday); so least no. of queries = 65,950
- w_27.csv - largest file ; 27th WeekOfYear ..was actually 1st week of July 2012.
It contains the maximum no. of queries = 236,892
- Observe the difference in number of queries (before/since the announcement of the news)

2.2.4 Future Work :-

The following includes few minor limitations and possible future options:

- When fields are mentioned implicitly in the search parameters, more arguments, not just 'author' or 'collections', could be parsed to include more views.

3. Conclusion

Favorite-Collections :-

- The proposed solution will allow a registered user to manage their favorite collections.
- A registered user is not restricted to the predefined list, but could access his/her own customized list of collections.
- This improves user's access time of a document, enriches user experience and provides flexibility to a CDS user.

Visualization of popular searched terms :-

- Users would find a new way to interact with CDS
- Different views on popular searched terms shall give flexibility to visualizations
- Popular search terms would change weekly, based on newer queries
- New patterns and events might be easier to find/predict.

4. References

[1] The Invenio Hacking guide;

<http://invenio-demo.cern.ch/help/hacking/>

[2] D3: Data-Driven Documents - Michael Bostock, Vadim Ogievetsky, Jeffrey Heer;

[Visualization and Computer Graphics, IEEE Transactions on](#)(Volume:17,Issue:12)

ISN 1077-2626; Pages 2301-2309;

[3] The Guardian; 'Higgs Boson discovered – live coverage';

<http://www.theguardian.com/science/blog/2012/jul/04/higgs-boson-discovered-live-coverage-cern>